

TOUGHENING OF SILICON NITRIDE MATRIX COMPOSITES BY THE ADDITION OF SI-C-N NANOMETER PARTICLES

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SUMMARY: In this paper, Si_3N_4 matrix composites reinforced by Si-C-N nanometer particles or SiC whiskers were fabricated using the hot-pressing technique. The mechanical properties of the composites containing various amounts of these Si-C-N nanometer particles were investigated. The maximum fracture toughness of these composites was $11.96 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$ and the flexural strength was 878.50 MPa after addition of 20 wt% of Si-C-N nanometer particles. It showed that the Si-C-N nanometer particles can remarkably improve the properties of Si_3N_4 matrix. Fracture surface and the micrographs of local intend areas were examined by SEM, the results revealed that the reinforcing mechanisms acting in these nanocomposites were crack deflection and crack branching by Si-C-N particles.

KEYWORDS: toughening, si-c-n nanometer particles, silicon nitride, fracture toughness, ceramic matrix composites

INTRODUCTION

Si_3N_4 and SiC ceramic are well known for their high strength, hardness and thermal stability, as well as the extreme brittleness that prevents their application in many critical components. The mechanical properties of these ceramics have been improved by the microstructure development, however, it seems to be difficult to expect the further improvement of mechanical properties by this technique. The need for further improvement in the mechanical properties has led to the development of high-strength and high-toughness ceramics, such as fiber-, whisker- and particulate- reinforced ceramic matrix composites[1,2]. SiC was used as a reinforcing material for Si_3N_4 more than 20 years ago[3], for the attempt to take advantage of the characteristics of both materials. Owing to process problems and the cost of SiC whiskers and fibers, the attention was being devoted to particulate composites. However, the use of SiC as uniform particles cannot improve noticeably the properties of the Si_3N_4 matrix.

Recently, researchers have found that the properties of ceramic can be dominantly improved by reducing particle sizes to nanometer levels, Niihara and his colleagues have been investigating the Si_3N_4 based nanocomposites, in which the nano-size SiC particles are dispersed mainly with the matrix grain[4-6], the flexural strength reaches 1550 MPa , the fracture toughness reaches $7.5 \text{ MPam}^{1/2}$. The materials are referred to as “nanocomposites” and the approach is generally indicated as a “new design concept” in the structure ceramic field. Research on nanometer particles toughening ceramic matrix composites becomes a new “hot point”.

In this paper, nanometer Si-C-N particle reinforced Si_3N_4 composites were made, the mechanical properties were measured, the phase structure was studied by XRD, the main goal was to improve the properties of Si_3N_4 matrix and to understand the reinforcing mechanisms of these nano-size SiC dispersed composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Fabrication of Composites

Si-C-N nanometer particles used as the reinforcing materials were made in our laboratory, through a Chemical Vapor Condensation (CVC) method, the average particle sizes were 70 nm, the total carbon in the particles was 24.08wt%, and the total nitrogen was 18.06wt%, Fig.1 showed the shape. As another reinforcing materials SiC whiskers with an average diameter of 0.6 μm were used, starting powders for the matrix material were Si_3N_4 (average particle size 1.0 μm), and La_2O_3 (average particle sizes 2.0 μm), Y_2O_3 (average particle size 0.5 μm).

As the Si-C-N nanometer particles contained many agglomerates which obstructed the densification of the composite, the particles must be through dispersion. This dispersion was executed by ultrasonication and stirring in alcohol. The SiC whiskers were pretreated using 50vol%HF + 50vol%HNO₃ for 30 minutes, then washed with deionized water. After the treatment, the Si-C-N nanometer particles and SiC whiskers were dried and used for the reinforcing materials.

The Si-C-N nanometer particles (or SiC whiskers) were mixed with the Si_3N_4 matrix powders which had been obtained by mixing of Si_3N_4 powder and sintering-aid powders in advance. The contents of the sintering-aid powders were 10wt% La_2O_3 and 10wt% Y_2O_3 with respect to the weight of the matrix powders. The powders were wet milled in alcohol for 24h, Si_3N_4 grinding media were used in all milling step. After drying, the obtained powders were sieved to under 100 mesh and were molded in a BN-coated graphite die for sintering. Hot-pressing was carried out at 1800 for 1h in a flowing nitrogen atmosphere under a pressure of 27.5 MPa for all composites. As comparison, monolithic Si_3N_4 with the same sintering-aid was also fabricated under the same conditions. Table 1 showed the contents of the composites.

Fig.1: The shape of Si-C-N nanometer particles

Table 1: The contents of the composites (wt%)

Sample	Si-C-N	SiC whiskers	Si ₃ N ₄	La ₂ O ₃	Y ₂ O ₃
S1	---	---	80	10	10
S2	10	---	70	10	10
S3	20	---	60	10	10
S4	---	20	60	10	10

Measurements of Composite Properties

Hot-pressed plate samples were cut into bars and polished for measuring the mechanical properties of the composites. Flexural strength were measured by three-point bending test, the sample size was 3mm x 4mm x 35mm, the span was 30mm. Fracture toughness was measured by a Single-End Straight-notch Beam (SENB) method, the sample size was 2.5mm x 2.5mm x 30mm, the notches were machined using a diamond blade 0.15mm wide deeply cut in the center.

Fracture toughness was also measured by an indentation fracture (IF) method. A surface flaw was made in the Well-polished specimens plane perpendicular to the hot-pressing axis by a standard diamond Vickers' indenter using a 19.6 KN load with a loading time of 20 seconds, K_{IC} values were calculated using the following equation:.

$$K_{IC}=0.142(c/a)^{-1.56}(E\Phi/H)^{2.5}Ha^{1/2}/\Phi \quad (1)$$

Where c is the radius of crack length, a is the impression radius, H is the hardness value calculated from the diagonal length, E is the Young's modulus of the composites, and Φ is the constraint factor (≈ 3). An average elastic modulus of 310GPa was assumed for the composites.

Density of the composites was measured by the Archimede's method using deionized water as the immersion medium, and their relative densities were evaluated using the theoretical densities calculated from simple mixing theory.

Results and Discussion

The Density and hardness of the composites reinforced with Si-C-N nanometer particles and SiC whiskers are listed in Table 2. All of the composites had densities higher than 3.2 g/cm³, indicating that the composites were densified using Y₂O₃-La₂O₃ sintering additives. The differences in relative density among these composites may be attributed to the presence of the Si-C-N nanometer particles, the results showed that the obstacle role of Si-C-N nanometer particles to the sintering of Si₃N₄ was more than that of SiC whiskers, and the sintering condition of Si-C-N nanometer particle reinforced Si₃N₄ composite wasn't very suitable, which should be studied further. The density and content of the composites will affect the hardness, with the density increasing, the hardness increases; with the SiC adding in, the hardness increases, it was confirmed by the values of hardness in Table 2.

Table 2: The Density of the composites

Sample	Measured density (kg/cm ³)	Calculated density (kg/cm ³)	Relative density (%)	Hardness (GPa)
S1	3.53	3.49	100	14.20
S2	3.41	3.43	99.42	14.17
S3	3.29	3.39	97.05	13.26
S4	3.42	3.39	100	15.57

The room-temperature flexural strength of the composites measured by three-point bending are listed in Table 3, varied from 689.9~878.5MPa, the fracture toughness values measured by both the SENB method and indentation fracture method are also listed in Table 3, the fracture toughness measured using SENB method varied from 8.27~11.24MPam^{1/2}. The result values of the indentation technique were lower than those of the SENB values, but the rules were the same. The fracture toughness showed strong dependence on the amount of the Si-C-N particles, the 10 wt% Si-C-N particles had no significant effect on the fracture toughness. In contrast, the 20wt% Si-C-N powder addition significantly improved toughness.

It is well known that the porosity of the composites will significantly affect the mechanical properties of Si₃N₄ matrix, it was very interesting that the density of S3 (reinforced with 20wt% Si-C-N nanometer particles) was the lowest, the relative density was only 97.05%, and the hardness was also the lowest, but the flexural strength and the fracture toughness values were the highest, even more than S4 (reinforced by 20wt% SiC whiskers). In Ref.7, the fracture toughness of SiC particle reinforced Si₃N₄ was improved significantly by the addition of SiC particles, but the flexural strength of the composite was decreased by introducing SiC particles. In this paper with the nano size Si-C-N adding, both of the toughness and the flexural strength were increased. It showed that the presence of Si-C-N nanometer particles make remarkable improvement of Si₃N₄ matrix, it revealed a bright prospect of nanocomposites.

Table 3: The mechanical properties of the composites

Sample	Item	Flexural strength (MPa)	Fracture toughness (MPam ^{1/2})	
			SENB	IF
S1		689.9	8.36	7.87
S2		785.4	8.27	7.72
S3		878.5	11.96	8.85
S4		804.8	11.24	8.78

Fig.2: The fracture surfaces of the composites (SEM)

The fracture surfaces of the composite examined by SEM are shown in Fig.2, It showed that intergranular fracture and “rough” fracture surfaces developed in all cases. The photos indicated that the morphology of Si_3N_4 grains in the nanocomposites was strongly influenced by the Si-C-N dispersions, the growth of of elongated Si_3N_4 grains was accelerated by the SiC dispersion, as compared with monolithic Si_3N_4 , the nanocomposites were composed of more uniform and homogeneous elongated Si_3N_4 grains. SiC whisker “pull-out” was observed in Fig.2d and elongated $\beta\text{-Si}_3\text{N}_4$ grain “pull-out” in other photos in Fig.2.

The micrographs of local intend areas examined by SEM are shown in Fig.3, it can be seen that the crack length of S3 and S4 was shorter than that of S1 and S2, this showed more evidence of why the fracture toughness of S3 and S4 were higher than that of S1 and S2.

The X-ray diffraction analyses of the composites revealed that the major phases were $\beta\text{-Si}_3\text{N}_4$ and $\beta\text{-SiC}$, Fig.4 shows the XRD parttern. Work is in process to characterize further the effect of phase structure of Si-C-N nanometer particles reinforced Si_3N_4 composites on their mechanical properties.

Fig.3: The micrographs of local interfacial areas (SEM)

CONCLUSIONS

1. Si-C-N nanometer particles has noticeable reinforcement to Si_3N_4 matrix, it can improve both of the fracture toughness and flexural strength.
2. The obstacle role of Si-C-N nanometer particles to the sintering of Si_3N_4 was more than that of SiC whiskers.
3. The fracture toughness showed strong dependence on the amount of the Si-C-N nanometer particles.
4. The reinforcing mechanisms acting in the Si-C-N nanometer particle reinforced Si_3N_4 composites were crack deflection and crack branching by Si-C-N particles.

Fig.4: The XRD of the composites

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